

Z-PINNING AND STITCHING OF COMPOSITES: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

M.J. Hiley¹, L.G. Stringer¹, M. Grassi¹, C. Jones¹ and M. Willows¹

¹*Applied Materials Group, QinetiQ Ltd, Cody Technology Park, Farnborough, Hampshire, GU14 0LX, England*

SUMMARY: The effect of through thickness reinforcement (TTR) on the in-plane and interlaminar properties of carbon fibre reinforced plastics has been investigated experimentally. Two methods of TTR including z-pinning with carbon fibre reinforced pins, and stitching with PBO (para-phenylene benzobisoxazole) fibres were evaluated. Results of the tests showed that in compression the mechanical properties, including those after impact, were broadly similar. Pinned laminates were marginally better in terms of their tensile properties. Laminates that had been pinned showed a slightly stiffer response when impacted compared to stitched laminates, but overall, the damage introduced was similar for a given impact energy. Mode I and mode II tests showed that z-pinning was more efficient at resisting damage growth compared to stitching. The work of fracture associated with pin pullout and pin fracture appeared to be greater than that required to fracture stitches.

To support and limit the amount of experimental testing required to characterize the TTR of a composite material a suitable modelling methodology has been outlined. Details of the finite element models currently being developed are briefly discussed.

KEYWORDS: Through-thickness reinforcement, z-pinning, stitching, modelling

INTRODUCTION

Delamination and debonding are the major failure modes in laminated composites, which significantly reduce the performance of a structure under compressive or bending loads. To overcome this problem, new composites with through-thickness reinforcement (TTR) have been used to improve the interlaminar strength and damage tolerance of laminated composites [1-8]. TTR has been shown to affect the structural behaviour and failure modes of composite laminates [9-14]. At a coupon level their large scale bridging process (LSB) start working only when delamination propagates into their field. TTR can provide non-linear bridging closure forces that shield the delamination crack from the full delaminating force and moment of the applied loads [15, 16].

The objective of this study was to compare the mechanical and physical properties of polymer composite laminates, reinforced by two types of TTR technologies: z-pinning and stitching. Laminates containing each type of through-thickness reinforcement were manufactured, the area density and diameter of the two reinforcements being matched as closely as possible. Pinning of the composite laminates was performed using carbon/bismaleimide pins with a 0.51mm diameter and 2% density. Stitching was performed with a PBO fibre thread, nominally 0.3mm in diameter (550g/10000m), using a lock stitch. Originally it was planned to stitch the laminates with stretch broken carbon fibres; however, practical difficulties encountered during stitching trials precluded this. In terms of mechanical properties, the tensile strength of the PBO fibres are substantially higher than those of the carbon fibres used

in the z-pins (typically 5.8GPa and 2.1GPa, respectively), but the stiffness of the PBO fibre thread is lower. In-plane compression and tensile tests were performed on the laminates containing each form of TTR, to establish the effect of each reinforcement on mechanical properties and the mechanisms of failure. Interlaminar tests were also performed, under mode I and mode II loading, to determine their influence on the initiation and growth of delaminations. The combined effect of in-plane and interlaminar stresses was evaluated by conducting compression after impact (CAI) tests. Examples of computational models being developed in parallel with the experimental study are also briefly discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Manufacturing details

Composite laminates (see Table 1) based on the carbon/epoxy prepreg IM7/8552, were manufactured using 0.51mm diameter z-pins, with a 2% density. An AZTEX UAZ-1000 Gantry mounted z-pinning machine, was used to insert the z-pins into the laminates. The z-pins were supplied mounted in a crushable foam preform. The principle of pin insertion involved crushing a foam preform containing the pins, using an ultrasonic head, in order to drive the pins into the uncured composite.

Fig. 1: Schematic showing z-pinning operation

Figure 1 shows a schematic diagram of the z-pinning apparatus which illustrates in more detail the insertion process. Localised heating of the pins and surrounding resin, occurred during pin insertion reducing the resin viscosity and assisting pin insertion. During insertion of the z-pins several of the outer plies were left off one side of the laminates. Once the pins had been inserted, the protruding part of each pin was removed, and the remaining plies were added to the stack. By adding several plies to the laminate after pinning, it was believed that the tendency of the pins to be angled over, due to consolidation of the laminate during curing, would be reduced; the pins pushing into the added surface plies during autoclaving helping to minimise this.

Similar laminates were manufactured and stitched using unlubricated 50/3 stretch broken Zylon PBO (Schappe Technology) fibre. A size 140 needle was used to stitch the laminates with a stitch spacing of 3.2mm; approximately the same spacing as between the z-pins. Figure 2 shows a photograph of the stitching equipment used. Prior to stitching, laminates were warmed in an oven to 60°C, to soften the resin, allowing easier insertion of the needle.

*Fig. 2: Photograph showing stitching of a laminate
(with permission of Ellis Developments Ltd, UK)*

Mechanical testing

In-plane tension and compression tests were performed and a comparison made between pinned and stitched laminates. Tests were also performed in compression after impact (CAI) to evaluate how each type of TTR influenced the initiation and growth of damage. Mode I, Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) tests, and mode II End Notched Flexure (ENF) fracture toughness tests were also performed to evaluate the effect of z-pinning and stitching on the initiation and propagation of delaminations. A summary of tests performed and laminate configurations assessed are shown in Table 1.

Test	Specimen gauge length/dimensions (mm)	Laminate Construction	Type of TTR assessed
In-plane tension	25 x 150	32 ply [(+45,0, -45, 90) ₄] _s	P, S
In-plane compression	25 x 25	32 ply [(+45,0, -45, 90) ₄] _s	P, S
Compression after Impact	50 x 150	32 ply [(+45,0, -45, 90) ₄] _s	P, S
Mode I (DCB)	25 x 200	24 ply [0 ₂ ,+45,-45,0, 90 ₂ ,0,-45,+45,0 ₂] _s	P, S
Mode II (ENF)	25 x 200	24 ply [0 ₂ ,+45,-45,0, 90 ₂ ,0,-45,+45,0 ₂] _s	P, S

P = Pinned (0.51mm), S = Stitched

Table 1: Summary of tests

Except where stated, all in-plane specimens were pinned across their entire surface area (with the exception of the end tabbed region). After end tabbing with glass fibre composite tabs, specimens were tested at a rate of 1mm/min in both compression and in tension. Specimens tested in compression were supported along their length using anti-buckling guides to prevent macro-buckling of the specimens.

Impacting of specimens was performed using an instrumented falling weight impactor, fitted with a 10mm hemi-spherical tup. Impacts were spaced at least 100mm apart to prevent damage from adjacent impacts overlapping. All impacts were undertaken with a nominal energy of 10J.

DCB and ENF tests were performed according to ESIS procedures, on 24 ply specimens containing a 10µm mid-plane (PTFE) insert. Unlike conventional DCB and ENF tests, which are usually performed on unidirectional laminates, a [+45, 0, -45, 90] laminate, containing a block of four 0° plies at the centre, was tested. A multidirectional laminate was chosen over a completely unidirectional laminate, to minimise splitting of the laminates. The multidirectional laminate was also considered more representative of those used in structural elements. To allow for precracking, specimens were designed so that a gap of approximately 10mm was left between the end of the starter film and the beginning of the pinned/stitched region. With the DCB tests, crack propagation was initiated directly from the insert, the crack growing from an unreinforced region into a pinned/stitched region. The mode II specimens were initially precracked in shear, the crack tip being grown across the 10mm section of unreinforced material, until it just reached the beginning of the pins or stitches. The specimen was then repositioned in the test fixture and loaded in an unstable configuration until the delamination grew. Using the failure load and corresponding displacement, the strain energy release rates G_{IC} and G_{IIC} were determined using beam theory. It was recognised that this

approach to data reduction did not fully capture the energy of fracture associated with pullout or fracture of the TTR. However, due to the simplicity of the method, and absence of any established data reduction methods for TTR reinforced materials, this approach was considered satisfactory to allow relative comparisons to be made between the different methods of TTR.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The results of the in-plane tests, performed on pinned and stitched specimens, are shown in Table 2. It was seen that z-pinning resulted in slightly higher values of tensile strength compared to equivalent stitched laminates, with no apparent difference in modulus. In compression, the stitched and pinned laminates gave almost identical values of failure strength and modulus. When the results of the compression after impact (CAI) results were studied, the z-pinned laminates were found to be marginally inferior in performance compared to the stitched laminate, but this difference was within the standard deviations.

Test type	Type of TTR	Failure Stress (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)	Failure Strain	Poissons Ratio
Plain tension 32 ply [(+,0, -, 90) ₄]s BS EN ISO 527-4:1997 250mm x25mm x 4mm (150mm gauge length)	P	680.4 (64.0)	60 (1.64)	1.10 (0.1)	0.31
	S	652.5 (32.4)	60.1 (1.0)	1.08 (0.02)	0.29
Plain compression 32 ply [(+,0, -, 90) ₄]s BS EN ISO 14126:1999 Type B2 125mm x 25mm x 4mm (25mm gauge length)	P	496.5 (30.5)	56.2 (0.6)	1.02 (0.07)	-
	S	498.5 (32.5)	57.5 (4.7)	1.06 (0.13)	-
Compression after impact CAI 32 ply [(+,0, -, 90) ₄]s	P	335.5 (10.2)	-	-	-
	S	344.1 (23.1)	-	-	-

P = Pinned (0.51mm), S = Stitched, (Figures in brackets are standard deviations)

Table 2: Summary of z-pinning results – In-plane tests

Figures 3 and 4 show ultrasonic C-scans of the impact sites present in the pinned and stitched laminates respectively. It was apparent from the scans that the damage in the stitched and pinned laminates were very similar in shape and size; the average areas of the impact sites was determined as 326.7mm² and 301.2mm², respectively.

Fig. 3: C-scan of impact sites z-pinned laminate

Fig. 4: C-scan of impact sites on stitched laminates

A comparison of force/deflection and force/time data recorded during the impacts, see Figure 5, showed that the z-pinned specimens were noticeably stiffer in their flexural response compared to the stitched specimens. For a given deflection, or time period, the peak force recorded for the pinned laminates was higher relative to the stitched material.

Fig. 5: Typical Force/Deflection and Force/Time Plots for impacted laminates

The results of the mode I interlaminar toughness tests, performed using the DCB test, are shown in Table 3. A comparison of the mode I results showed that there was very little difference in energy required to initiate delamination growth into the pinned and stitched regions of composite; also both gave substantially higher initiation values compared to unpinned material (initiation was defined as the point when the crack reached the first pin or stitch). When, however, the energy required to propagate the delamination was considered it was apparent that the z-pinned laminate performed better than the stitched laminate.

Laminate Type	Mean G_{IC} (Initiation) (J/m^2)	Mean G_{IC} (Max Load) (J/m^2)
Plain (unpinned)	261 (31.0)	-
Pinned	984 (142)	4448 (598)
Stitched	990 (300)	2940 (500)

Table 3: Summary of mode I test results

Figure 6 shows typical load versus displacement traces for the two materials and the baseline. The initial portion of the curve represented crack growth within the unpinned/unstitched region, which was present on all samples 10 millimetres in front of the insert. With the pinned and stitched laminates, the load then picked up substantially (at a displacement of around 4mm), as the crack front grew into the pinned and stitched zones (developing zone). Once the

crack front had grown into a fully stitched or pinned region (developed zone), both TTR methods showed slip/stick behaviour, which was attributed to fracture of pins or stitches respectively.

Fig. 6 Load/Displacement traces for plain, pinned and stitched laminates. (Inset) Stitched and pinned DCB specimens

Figure 7 shows typical R-curves for the three types of material tested. Whilst the unreinforced material had a very flat profile, the toughness of the material hardly changing as a function of crack length, the laminates with TTR showed a substantial rise in G_{IC} before stabilising.

Fig. 7: R Curves for plain, pinned and stitched laminates

Table 4 shows the fracture toughness G_{IIC} of the three materials determined using the ENF test. It was apparent that the z-pinned laminates gave initiation values of fracture toughness more than twice that of the stitched laminate and five times that of the unreinforced material.

Laminate Type	Mean G_{IIC} (Initiation) (J/m^2)
Plain (unpinned)	745.1 (97.8)
Pinned	3510.3 (221)
Stitched	1507.4 (109.1)

Table 4: Summary of mode II test results

MODELLING PROCEDURE

As well as the experimental analysis, within the current study computational models are also being developed. Computational models are aimed at supporting and limiting the amount of experimental testing required to characterise the TTR composite material. In the following sections details of the modelling methodology are presented, and the finite element models being developed are briefly discussed.

Modelling Methodology

For the insertion of a new material system into a structural component, the development of reliable computational models that can predict the material mechanical and failure behaviour is very beneficial. Their general applicability and validity must then be demonstrated at different structural levels of the pyramid approach [17]. This concept of a building block approach involves a step-by-step validation of the numerical models from coupon to structural levels [18].

FE Model Scale (mm)	$0.14 < x < 3$	$1.4 < x < 100$	$4 < x < 400$	$10 < x < 1000$
FE Model Output	$0.14 < x < 3$	$1.4 < x < 100$	$4 < x < 400$	$10 < x < 1000$
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Unit cell models for stiffness and stress analysis ▪ TTR micro-mechanics and bridging laws ▪ TTR failure modes 				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ TTR interface element implementation ▪ Coupon delamination growth ▪ Fracture Mechanics ▪ TTR large scale bridging 				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ TTR structural joint analysis. ▪ Structural Joint strength ▪ Structural joint damage tolerance 				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Global-local FE analysis ▪ TTR effect on damage growth ▪ Damage tolerance of structural components 				

Table 5: Modelling methodology for TTR materials and structures.

These predictive computational models once validated by experimental evidence can significantly cut the time and costs associated with the material certification process. A schematic graph of the modelling methodology adopted in this study, is presented in Table 5.

On the first row and first column respectively, the different model scales and the model outputs sought are described. Firstly, the meso-level modelling has a characteristic geometrical length equal to one z-pin radius. The definition as meso-level is due to the fact that a single TTR is represented as a homogeneous continuum without the distinct representation of its constituents (fibres and matrix); hence its definition as meso-modelling. At this level of analysis the periodic structure of the TTR composite laminate can be described by a Representative Volume Element (RVE) in isolation. It is therefore assumed that a uniform external load applied to a periodic structure will produce stress and strain distributions that are also periodic. The material response to external loads in terms of stiffness, strength and TTR failure in the crack wake during delamination growth is therefore derived from the RVE analysis with suitable applied boundary conditions.

Secondly, the coupon modelling level is pursued to analyse the enhancement of delamination resistance - the effect of material and geometrical parameters on the structural fracture toughness. The coupon level model is validated using experimental data. The large scale bridging and energy absorption mechanisms of TTR during delamination growth are simulated by using several interface element formulations. The current programme of work has been focusing on these first two levels of analysis as it aligns well with the experimental work.

It is envisaged that in a future study the modelling will be extended to structural sub-components and components to investigate the TTR effect on the component strength and damage tolerance. The structural element computational model will contain the validated computational models via a global-local approach.

Meso-Modelling Details

Representative RVE were developed using two different commercially available finite element codes: LS-DYNA and Abaqus. Within LS-DYNA the modelling approach taken was to determine the basic engineering properties of the z-pinned (and un-pinned) quasi-isotropic laminate from the stiffness or C-matrix. Determination of each 'C' value was obtained by applying a unit load to the RVE model with suitable periodic boundary conditions. In the first set of simulations, the RVE model represented a section of the quasi-isotropic laminate without any z-pins and, in the second set of simulations, a single z-pin was introduced into the RVE model to enable the effect of the z-pins on the laminate engineering properties to be determined. This simulation was repeated to obtain the stiffness matrix for laminate stacking-sequences with and without TTR.

A TTR RVE FE model was also developed using Abaqus in order to simulate the bridging micro-mechanics provided by the TTR during delamination growth. The bridging mechanics were simulated by assuming a constant friction coefficient at the interface along the TTR axial direction and using improved contact-elements to solve the frictional contact problem. Different loading conditions are considered in order to study the TTR bridging behaviour under pure mode I loading, mode II shear loading and mixed mode loading conditions. In Figure 8 an example of a mode I simulation is provided.

(a) (b) (c)

Figure 8: Through-thickness reinforcement (TTR) pull-out process from a laminate; (a) TTR elastic stretching; (b) TTR debonding; (c) TTR frictional sliding.

The FE output for this model will mainly be related to the TTR bridging curves, which include elastic deformation with a fully/partially bonded interface plus frictional sliding. Two quasi-isotropic sub-laminates were modelled using 8-noded brick elements and contact elements between the two delamination surfaces, which can potentially come into contact under mixed-mode loading conditions. The epoxy pocket surrounding the z-pins was assumed to have a circular shape and a constant thickness. The z-pin was modelled with a mesh bias towards the centre in order to increase the accuracy of the stress results at the delamination plane. Contact elements were also defined between the the TTR external surface and the surrounding matrix. The model was formulated in order to be valid for different kind of through-thickness reinforcements (TTR): z-pins or stitches; the difference in the model being in the applied boundary conditions, and TTR element mesh.

DISCUSSION

The results of in-plane tests has shown that that the type of reinforcement used had little effect on the compressive properties of laminates both in terms of longitudinal strength or stiffness. Previous studies [6, 8, 11] on pinned laminates has shown that during pin insertion a variety of different defects are introduced into the laminate, including fibre fracture and fibre waviness. Such defects have been reported to reduce in-plane properties; tensile and compressive strength values of plain and pinned specimens typically falling by 20% and 5% respectively [8]. Such defects also arise during stitching [9]. These defects influence failure in a complex manner depending on the type of in-plane loading applied, and which type of interlaminar forces are acting on the material [8]. In plain compression specimens, the primary mechanism of failure is usually fibre microbuckling. Both the stitching and pinning processes would have resulted in local lateral distortions of the fibre around the TTR making the laminates more prone to collapse. Since the pin and stitch diameters were similar, the amount of lateral fibre distortion expected around each stitch or pin are likely to be similar; hence their influence on compression strength would be similar.

The slightly increased tensile strengths observed in the pinned laminates, compared with the stitched laminates, can also be attributed to local defects caused by insertion of the TTR. A possible mechanism for this is that, although both processes cause fibre fracture, the stitching is likely to have led to more fibre fracture, due to the higher speed of insertion of the stitches compared with the z-pinning process [6, 9]. Since each zone of fibre fracture acts as a stress concentration, the stitched specimens with their greater fibre damage, might be expected to have a poorer performance.

As with the plain compression results, the type of TTR employed had little effect on the compression after impact results. Although the z-pinned laminate showed a slightly stiffer flexural response compared to the stitched laminate during impacting, the size of the impact damage produced was similar in both laminates. It is possible that the larger deflections, and hence greater strains developed in the composite, might have led to more matrix cracking in

the stitched laminates, but this was not observed visually, or on the C-scans, and was not reflected significant in the mechanical properties.

Mode I and mode II interlaminar fracture toughness measurements showed that z-pinning was much more effective at resisting delamination growth compared with stitching; although both methods brought substantial improvements in fracture toughness compared with unreinforced composite. Previous studies [8], however, suggest that with pinned laminates, the angle and depth of pin penetration can influence the R-curve considerably. The reason for the difference in the interlaminar properties of the two forms of TTR is not yet fully understood, but a contributory factor may be the difference in stiffness between the PBO and z-pin carbon fibres (typically 180GPa and 224GPa, respectively). The more flexible nature of the stitch compared with the carbon may have allowed delaminations to form around the stitches and coalesce earlier on in the loading cycle. This would be the case under both opening and shear loading modes. The same study [8] also showed that z-pinning can also give rise to small improvements in CAI values, strengths of plain laminates reportedly rising from 315MPa to 349 MPa after pinning (0.51mm/2%). Compared to a baseline value of 315MPa, both TTR's also produced improved values of CAI, although the increase did not reflect the large increases in G_{IC} and G_{IIC} . A more detailed fractographic examination of the samples using electron microscopy is required, to understand the complex mechanisms driving failure under different loading scenarios and TTR configurations. This understanding will also be greatly enhanced when the computational models are further developed.

CONCLUSIONS

The in-plane tensile and compressive properties of laminates, both plain and impacted, were measured and the mechanical properties and failure mechanisms compared. The effect of TTR on interlaminar properties was evaluated by testing laminates in compression after impact (CAI) and in mode I (opening) and mode II (shear) using the DCB and ENF test, respectively. Results of the tests showed that in compression the mechanical properties, including after impact, were broadly similar. Pinned laminates were marginally better in terms of their tensile properties. During impacting, the pinned laminates showed a slightly stiffer response compared to stitched laminates, but the overall damage introduced into the specimens was similar. Interlaminar tests showed that z-pinning was more efficient at resisting damage growth compared to stitching. The work of fracture associated with pin pullout and pin fracture appeared to be greater than that required to yield and fracture the lower modulus stitches. Computational models are currently being developed at a meso-scale and coupon-scale and will be validated against the experimental data generated within this study.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the financial support of the UK MoD. The assistance of Andy Foreman with the impacting studies is also gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

1. Dow, M.B., Smith, D.L., 'Improving the delamination resistance of CFRP by stitching carbon fabrics', *Int. SAMPE Technical Conf. Series*, Vol.21: 595-605, 1989.
2. Jain, L. K. and Mai, Y. W. "On the effect of the stitching on Mode I delamination toughness of laminated composites" *Composite Science and Technology*, Vol. 51, pp. 331-345, 1994.

3. Farley GL & Dickinson LC. "Mechanical response of composite materials with through-the-thickness reinforcement." NASA CR-14753, 123-143, 1993.
4. Freitas G, Fusco T, Campbell T, Harris J & Rosenberg S. "Z-Fiber™ Technology and products for enhancing composite design." 83rd Meeting of AGARD SMP, 1996, CP-590.
5. Cartié D.D.R. and Partridge I.K., 'Delamination behaviour of Z-pinned laminates' In: J.G. Williams and A. Pavan, Editors, *Proceedings of Second ESIS TC4 conference, Les Diablerets, Switzerland, 13–15 September ESIS Publication*, 2000, ISBN 008 043710-9, 1999.
6. Partridge I.K., Cartie, D.D.R. & Bonnington, T., 'Manufacture and Performance of Z-pinned Laminates Composites', In 'Advanced Polymeric Materials', Edited by Shonaike & Advani, Chapter 3, pp103-138, CRC Press (Publisher), ISBN 1-58716-047, 2003.
7. Greenhalgh E. and Hiley M.J., 'The assessment of novel materials and processes for the impact tolerant design of stiffened composite aerospace structures', *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, Volume 34, Issue 2, 151-161, 2003.
8. Stringer, L.G. and Hiley, M.J., "Through-thickness reinforcement of composites: Z-pinning, Stitching, and 3D weaving", *14th International Conference for Composite Materials*, ICCM14, 11-14 July, San Diego, CA, 2003.
9. Mouritz A.P., Leong K.H. and Herszberg I. "A review of the effect of stitching on the in-plane mechanical properties of fibre-reinforced polymer composites" *Composites Part A*, 28A, 979-991, 1999.
10. Grassi M., Zhang X. and Meo M., 'Prediction of stiffness and stresses in z-fibre reinforced composite laminates', *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, Volume 33, Issue 12, 2002, 1653-1664.
11. Partridge I.K., Cartié, D.D.R., Troulis, M., Grassi M. and Zhang, X. 'Evaluating the mechanical effectiveness of Z-pinning', *Proceedings of SAMPE /Dayton Technical Conference*, 2003.
12. Clarke, A, Greenhalgh, E, Meeks, C & Jones C, 'Enhanced Structural Damage Tolerance Of CFRP Primary Structures By Z Pin Reinforcement', 44th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference, Norfolk, AIAA-2003-1679, April 2003.
13. Allegri, G, & Zhang, X, 'Delamination/Debond Growth in Z-Fibre Reinforced Composite T-Joint: A Finite Element Simulation', 11th European Conference on Composite Materials, Rhodes, Greece, 2004.
14. Grassi M., Clarke A., Kehmiri N. and Gaitonde M. 'Analysis of through-thickness reinforcements effects on the failure modes of a composite rib foot', 11th European Conference on Composite Materials, Rhodes, Greece, 2004.
15. Grassi M. and Zhang X., 'Finite element analyses of mode I interlaminar delamination in z-fibre reinforced composite laminates, *Composites Science and Technology*', Volume 63, Issue 12, 1815-1832, 2003.
16. P. Robinson and S. Das, 'Mode I DCB testing of composite laminates reinforced with z-direction pins: a simple model for the investigation of data reduction strategies', *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, Volume 71, Issue 3, 345-364, 2004.
17. Rouchon, J., Certification of large airplane composite structures. In: *Recent progress and new trends and compliance philosophy*, ICAS, Vol.2, 1990. 1439-1447.
18. Roudolff, F., and Gadke, M., Damage tolerance of composite structures for large transport aircraft. *Aerospace Science Technology*, 4, 2000, 23-32.